

FATIGUE OF WEB-CORE COMPOSITE BRIDGE DECKS: AN EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Glass fibre-polymer composite (a.k.a GFRP) bridge decks are gaining popularity as a renovation option for highway bridges due to their fatigue resistance, corrosion resistance, and favorable strength-to-weight ratio. However, current design codes tend to result in overly conservative designs. To achieve reliable and optimized bridge concepts with composite decks, understanding the failure behaviour of these decks is crucial. Web-core deck panels utilize UD-dominated multi-directional, connected by equidistant webs are dominantly used. This study presents an experimental and numerical investigation of composite web-core deck panel failure under static and fatigue loading, comparing failure modes and strength predictions.

KEYWORDS

Bridge Decks; Web-core panels; Experimental Investigation; Fatigue loading; Numerical simulation

INTRODUCTION

The infrastructure industry is currently searching for innovative and sustainable solutions that could be applied in the renovation of existing bridges and the development of new projects. As an alternative to traditional materials, Glass Fibre-Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) bridge decks have emerged as a promising solution due to their excellent fatigue and corrosion resistance, high strength-to-weight ratios, and low thermal expansion. Despite their numerous advantages, current design codes often lead to overdesigned solutions, resulting in increased costs and complexity in bridge construction.

One very popular GFRP bridge decks design includes web-core panels, engineered using multi-directional composite laminates, primarily unidirectional (UD), to provide adequate bending resistance. More specifically, these facings are connected by quasi-isotropic, equidistant webs that transfer shear forces and reduce local buckling. Additionally, a foam core is also utilised as it has been demonstrated to considerably enhance the mechanical performance of the bridge deck (Zi & Kim, 2007) by supporting the webs in the lateral direction.

Past studies have demonstrated the anisotropic behaviour of these sandwich web-core panels for bridge decks, with linear behaviour noted for the longitudinally directed webs (Kulpa & Siwowski, 2019) and non-linear behaviour observed when the webs were oriented in the other direction (Park et al., 2005; Zi & Kim, 2007). Initially, this non-linearity in the transverse direction was attributed to weak web-flange joints (Davalos et al., 1996; Park et al., 2005), but subsequent research pointed towards shear deformation of the rectangular units as the primary cause (Zi et al., 2008). Despite the critical role of these webs in load transfer, research on their fatigue performance has been primarily focused on webs oriented in the transverse direction.

Interestingly, even though vehicle loads are primarily transferred in the longitudinal direction, comprehensive understanding of the fatigue performance of bridge decks with interconnected webs oriented in this direction is lacking. This study seeks to address this gap by investigating the fatigue

performance of bridge decks with webs in the longitudinal direction through a 3-point bending test. It is hypothesized that these longitudinally-oriented webs may present unique behaviours under fatigue loading.

Understanding these behaviours is crucial for improving global fatigue performance and, ultimately, the safety and longevity of the GFRP bridge decks. Therefore, this study will also review the static behaviour of the deck prior to its cyclic response for representative traffic loads on highway bridges. A numerical investigation using Finite Element Modelling (FEM) will be carried out to gain insights into the interplay of various failure mechanisms. By comparing failure modes in static and fatigue tests, this study aims to provide a comprehensive assessment of the performance of composite web-core deck panels under various loading scenarios. The findings from this investigation will aid in the development of improved design guidelines for the use of GFRP composites in bridge construction, ultimately leading to more sustainable, cost-effective, and resilient infrastructure.

TEST SETUP, PROCEDURE AND INSTRUMENTATION

Specimen description

The experimental investigation focuses on the static and fatigue analysis of bridge decks. The dimensions of the specimens used in the experiment are illustrated in Figure 1. All the composite deck panels employed in the study are manufactured by FiberCore Europe using stitched bonded fabrics and vacuum infusion techniques.

The bridge deck segments consist of webcore panels, which incorporate polyurethane (PU) foam blocks. A Z-shape layup technique is employed to construct these panels, incorporating three types of fabrics. The PU foam blocks are wrapped with [+/-45] E-glass fabrics, and three layers of E-glass UD fabrics along the length direction are added with a two-block overlap at the top and bottom of each block. The Z-shape layup further involves the placement of two layers of E-glass [0/90] fabrics with a 2.5-block overlap. Table 1 provides the isotropic elastic material properties of the UD plies that make up the laminated top and bottom face sheets (facings) and the webs. These properties are obtained from standard material tests conducted by the panel producer. Once the reinforcement layers are properly positioned, the polyurethane resin is infused through two runners located 317.5 mm from the edge of the deck.

Figure 1: Bridge deck segment dimensions. Distances are in mm.

Table 1: Material properties of UD plies

Property	Elastic FRP UD ply – $V_f = 54\%$ - in facings	Elastic FRP UD ply – $V_f = 27\%$ - in webs
Longitudinal modulus, E_1 (GPa)	42	22
Transverse modulus, E_2 (GPa)	14,5	8
Shear modulus, G_{12} (GPa)	4,2	3,5
Poissons ratio, ν_{12}	0.27	0.27
Density, (kg/m^3)	1962	1576

Test description

The experimental setup is conducted within the blue frame of the Stevin Laboratory II at TU Delft, as depicted in Figure 2. Figure 2 illustrates the actual test setup, which includes a specially designed loading steel frame to accommodate the specimen. All specimens undergo loading in a three-point bending configuration, with a span of 2 m with the webs in the longitudinal direction. The jack employed in the experiment has a maximum stroke capacity of 100 mm and a maximum pressure capacity of 1000 kN. To allow for minor lateral displacement and prevent torsion within the bridge deck, the bridge deck is supported by two rollers. Steel plates with dimensions of 150x600x30 mm, along with an additional 10 mm thick cork layer, are utilized between the rollers and the bridge deck to avoid force concentrations around the supports.

For applying the load, a steel plate with dimensions of 600x320x25 mm (in initial tests) and 600x320x50 mm (in subsequent tests) is used. An interlayer of cork is added between the steel plate and the bridge deck. The dimensions of the wheel load are determined based on the heaviest wheel load observed within the Eurocode for LM 4 (European committee for Standardization, 2021), as shown in Figure 3. Previous research (Sebastian et al., 2017) has demonstrated that the use of a cork layer provides uniform force distribution compared to a rubber layer. By incorporating cork between the steel plate and the deck, stress concentrations at the loading point, which is positioned at the midspan of the panel, are minimized.

The tests are performed load controlled and the loads are measured until the deck completely failed. A total of 4 specimens have been tested: 2 static and 2 fatigue tests. Firstly, the static tests are performed with a monotonic loading of 2.5 mm/min to failure. The peak loads of the tests provided and estimate of ultimate static capacity, F_{ult} of the decks. The fatigue tests are performed at the load ratio of $R=0.1$ at the rate of 1Hz. The maximum fatigue load is chosen as 60% of F_{ult} .

Figure 2: Test setup with DIC and LP systems installed.

Figure 3: Wheel load LM4 Eurocode.

In order to measure displacements and deformations of the specimens, multiple systems are employed. The static tests utilize a combination of 3D Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system, a fibre optic system, and linear potentiometers (LP). During the cyclic testing LP are applied and periodic images are captured by a single camera throughout the test duration.

The 3D DIC system is employed to accurately quantify the strain on the top layer of the bridge deck. To ensure comprehensive results, two DIC systems are positioned with an overlap (Figure 2), allowing for the combination of data between the two systems. These measurements provide valuable insight into the stress experienced at the point of failure and the distribution across the entire bridge deck.

In addition, a distributed fibre optic system, developed by Luna Innovations (Luna Innovations Incorporated, 2023), shown in Figure 4, is embedded on the top of the deck. This system includes two optical fibres installed along the entire length of the bridge deck. These fibres monitor the elongation of the structure, providing a comprehensive analysis of its behaviour. By comparing the data from the fibre optic system with the results obtained from the DIC systems, a more complete understanding of the bridge deck's response to stress can be achieved. Notably, the arrangement of the optical fibres allows for specific measurement of elongation under the wheel load.

To measure the precise vertical deformation of the deck, four linear potentiometers (LP) are employed. These LPs are placed at three distinct locations on the bridge deck depending on the loading protocol: at the midpoint (LP2 and LP3), at one-quarter of the total length (LP4 and LP5) and in proximity of the supports (LP1 and LP6) as shown in Figure 5. During the static tests LP2, LP3, LP 4 and LP5 are utilized. During the fatigue tests LP1, LP2, LP3 and LP6 are utilized for measurement purposes.

Figure 4: Optical fibers a) pattern, b) glued at the top of the deck.

Figure 5: Potentiometers layout. Load and supports.

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Prior to conducting the tests, Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is conducted on the bridge deck to determine the maximum failure loads and corresponding displacements. Given the large scale of the testing specimens and the intricate structural behaviour of sandwich panels, it is crucial to analyze complex structures using analytical methods and FEA before initiating the experimental campaign.

FEA enables us to obtain a preliminary understanding of the experimental setups, anticipated failure modes, and the necessary capacity of the testing machines. This analysis allows for an initial impression and idea regarding the model, boundary conditions, input loads, and overall analysis approach.

In this section, we provide a detailed description of the FEA model, including the specified boundary conditions, input loads, and the analysis procedure undertaken.

Description of model

For the modelling and analysis of the bridge deck, ABAQUS/Explicit software is employed. The laminates of the webs, as well as the facings of the decks, are represented using 2-D orthotropic linear elastic non-layered shell S4R elements. The material properties of the laminates are equivalent anisotropic properties obtained from homogenized laminate properties, as indicated in Table 2, and are implemented in the model.

The steel plate that represents the wheel load is modelled using shell S4R elements, with linear elastic properties assigned to them (Young's modulus of 210 GPa and $\nu=0.3$). The steel plate is positioned at the mid-span of the deck. The mesh for the deck and the steel plate is generated with a finite element size of 10 mm, resulting in 16 linear elements over the height of the web.

To reduce computational time, only half of the deck is modelled using the symmetry plane. In this symmetry plane (YZ-plane), in-plane rotations and translations are restricted ($U1=UR2=UR3=0$). In the regions of the supports, the bottom facing of the deck is coupled to the reference points. On one side, two translations (vertical and lateral) at reference point RP-1 are restrained, while on the opposite side of the deck, only vertical displacements are restricted at RP-2. All rotations are allowed. The boundary conditions and interactions in the model are depicted in Figure 6.

A tie constraint is utilized between the steel plate and the deck, where the centerline of the steel plate is coupled to the reference point RP-3 using a kinematic constraint. The load is applied as imposed vertical displacement on RP3 reference point.

To reduce errors in the post-processing of the results, the facings and webs of the deck are assigned a local coordinate system.

Table 2: Homogenised material properties for FEA.

Property	Facings	Webs
Longitudinal modulus, E_1 (GPa)	33.06	12.75
Transverse modulus, E_2 (GPa)	22.43	12.75
Shear modulus, G_{12} (GPa)	4.2	5.03
Poissons ratio, ν_{12}	0.19	0.27
Strength in longitudinal direction, σ_1 (MPa)	397	153
Strength in longitudinal direction, σ_2 (MPa)	269	153
Shear Strength, τ_{12} (MPa)	67.2	80.3

Figure 6: Assembly and finite element model boundary conditions.

Results

The FEA conducted on the deck has successfully predicted the force-deflection behavior, as evidenced by the comparison with experimental results shown in Figure 9. The linear deflections of the deck observed during testing closely resemble those predicted by the FEA. To determine the maximum deflections, the applied load is measured using RP-3.

In order to assess the structural integrity of the deck, the governing stresses in the facings and webs are analyzed. The maximum stresses observed are presented in Figure 7 for the facings and Figure 8 for the webs. The analysis follows the guidelines outlined in CUR 96 (CROW-CUR Recommendation 96:2019), with a linear stress limit of 1.2% and a shear stress limit of 1.6% based on the material strength.

The FEA results indicate that failure is likely to occur in the webs due to shear stress when an applied load of 359kN is reached. On the other hand, the analysis of the facings suggests that failure is expected due to compression at a load of 480kN. It's important to note that the FEA does not account for the foam core blocks present in the actual structure, which contribute to enhancing local buckling resistance and shear strength of the webs.

The presence of the foam core blocks reduces the possibility of shear buckling in the webs at a load of 441kN in specimen S1. It should be acknowledged that the remaining FEA results deviate by approximately 20% and 12% when compared to the experimental data. However, this disparity can be attributed to the omission of the foam core blocks in the analysis, which could affect the overall structural behavior of the deck.

Figure 7: Maximum tensile and compressive stresses in the facings.

Figure 8: Maximum shear stress in the webs.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Static flexure test

Two static three-point bending tests, referred to as S1 and S2, are conducted using the setup depicted in Figure 2. The tests are carried out to identify the ultimate loads F_{ult} . The load-deflection curve in Figure 9 illustrates the behavior of the decks. The deflection shows nearly linear characteristics, with the S1 specimen failing under a load of 441 kN and a displacement of 38 mm, while the S2 specimen fails under a load of 545 kN and a displacement of 53 mm. The average displacement of the two potentiometers in the middle of the deck is considered for analysis.

During the first test (S1), significant bending of the load plate is observed. This plastic deformation results in increased force at the center of the wheel load (Sebastian et al., 2017) and decreased load at the ends. Although the curved plate better represents the actual wheel load, it does not provide consistent loading of the bridge segments. As a result, after the initial test (S1), a redesign of the setup is performed with an increased thickness of the steel plate to 50 mm. The changes to the plate introduce different local stresses, leading to diverse failure mechanisms.

During test S1, both bending and lateral shear are observed in the specimen. Figure 10, displaying the potentiometer results, indicates that the backside experiences greater deflection compared to the front sides of the test piece. Three failure mechanisms are identified during the test, as shown in Figure 11. These mechanisms include web buckling, top layer buckling, and shear failure at the supports. The initial DIC results in Figure 12 suggest that top layer buckling is the primary failure mechanism, followed by the occurrence of the other two failure mechanisms, aligning with expectations for the

test. Upon visual inspection of the S1 sample, initial imperfections are discerned in the region of the runners. These defects appear to cause a premature damage to the sample.

During the test S2 no bending of the load plate is observed. The LP results, shown in Figure 10, indicate that no shear occurred in this test. Visual inspection indicate that the failure of the specimen occurred due to top-facing buckling, as confirmed by DIC in Figure 14. The occurrence of a small nonlinear behavior prior to failure further supports the buckling failure mode, aligning with the initial estimations. The absence of initial imperfections and lateral shear likely contributed to the higher ultimate load observed in this test.

Figure 15 presents an overview of the strain distribution on the top surface of the specimen at a load of 158kN in test S2. The strains are depicted using different measurement devices and modeling techniques. Both DIC and optical fiber measurements exhibit excellent agreement with the FEA and with each other for regions outside the loading plate. However, discrepancies are observed between FEM and optical fiber measurements beneath the loading plate, while DIC data does not provide any information regarding these points.

Figure 9: Load-Deflection plot for static tests and FEA.

Figure 10: Deck displacements from potentiometers. Static test.

a) Shear delamination above the support b) lateral shear cracks in the foam c) kinking of the web

Figure 11: Failure mechanisms in the test S1.

a) Before failure
b) After failure
Figure 12: Top facing strains by DIC in test S1. Limit at -0.8%.

a) Delamination top facing due to buckling
b) Buckling top facing
Figure 13: Failure mechanisms in the test S2.

a) Before failure
b) During failure
c) After failure
Figure 14: Top facing strains by DIC in test S2. Limit at -0.8%.

Figure 15: Top facing strains in the test S2 by optical fibres, DIC and FEA.

Fatigue test

The results of the two tested decks, referred as F1 and F2, are very consistent in terms of response and behaviour. Both fatigue tests resulted in the same failure mechanism of the delamination at the bottom facing and the crack development through the whole width of the sample, as shown in Figure 15.

Sample F1 failed after 11844 cycles and sample S2 – after 10724 cycles under the load of $F_{max} = 300$ kN. The F_{max} is identified as 60% of the average of F_{ult} of the tests S1 and S2. Therefore sample

S1 is also used for testing set up maintenance and it is run 80 cycles under the stepped load of 30 kN and 200 cycles under the sinusoidal load of 150kN. The run of the F1 test under the lower loads could result in the higher fatigue life of the F1 compared to F2 by 1000 cycles. Also the changes in the applied loads on the specimen F1 are visible on stiffness degradation plot in Figure 17, with a peak load of 315 kN applied at 280 cycles, which stabilised to the required load of 300 kN.

The degradation of the structural properties during the fatigue loading is periodically monitored. Stiffness K_i of the sample is assessed at cycles N_i and Figure 17 shows the evolution of the normalised stiffness K_i/K_0 , where K_0 is the one obtained in the initial cycle. It can be seen that the first 10000 cycles resulted in a stiffness reduction of 15%, followed by a maximum stiffness drop of 25% near the failure.

Figure 16: Failure mechanisms due to fatigue.

Figure 17: Stiffness of the decks.

CONCLUSION

This experimental and numerical study addressed the static and fatigue performances of web-core composite bridge decks with longitudinal webs. From experimental and numerical results it is found that the deck response of the load versus deflections are linear until failure. The panels mainly displayed a linear-elastic behaviour, indicating that excessive overstress applied to the panels would not lead to permanent damage.

Distinct failure mechanisms emerged from the application of different loading protocols. In the static tests, failure modes such as lateral shear, web buckling, and top-facing buckling were identified. These failure modes align with the predictions made by the numerical analysis, which indicated that shear in the web or compression in the top facings were likely causes of failure. Conversely, the fatigue tests consistently resulted in delamination of the bottom facing under tension. The static tests exhibited varying and complex failure modes, whereas the fatigue tests exhibited uniform failure patterns.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.